

Islamic Finance: What is the Outlook for Italy?

Authors : Paolo Pietro Biancone

Abstract : The spread of Islamic financial instruments is an opportunity to offer integration for the immigrant population and to attract, through the specific products, the richness of sovereign funds from the "Arab" countries. However, it is important to consider the possibility of comparing a traditional finance model, which in recent times has given rise to many doubts, with an "alternative" finance model, where the ethical aspect arising from religious principles is very important.

Keywords : banks, Europe, Islamic finance, Italy

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